

Anatomical Locking Compression Plate versus Dynamic Compression Plate in the Treatment of Displaced Midshaft Clavicle Fractures in Adults

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Abstract

Background: Midshaft fractures account for between 69 and 82 per cent of all cases of clavicle fracture, which are among the most frequent orthopedic injuries. Displaced midshaft clavicular fractures are traditionally managed non-operatively. However, conservative treatment has been shown to result in higher rates of nonunion, malunion and poor functional outcomes. Consequently, there has been a shift toward surgical fixation to enhance union rates and improve shoulder function. Among surgical options, plate fixation is widely favored for its reliability, though the choice between anatomical locking compression plates (LCP) and dynamic compression plates (DCP) remains debated. **Aim:** The aim is to compare the short-term clinical outcomes of using anatomical LCP and DCP to treat displaced midshaft clavicle fractures in adults. **Methods:** A prospective randomized clinical trial was conducted at Al-Imamein Al-Kadhimaiein Medical City in Baghdad, Iraq, from January 2021 to January 2022. Twenty adult patients with unilateral displaced midshaft clavicle fractures were randomly assigned to two groups: Group A (LCP) and Group B (DCP). **Results:** The mean age was 26.8 ± 3.9 years, with males comprising 65% of the sample. No significant difference was observed in wound infection rates between groups ($P = 0.839$). However, symptomatic hardware prominence was significantly higher in the DCP group ($P = 0.039$). The LCP group demonstrated a significantly shorter time to union, though both groups achieved a 100% union rate. Quick DASH scores favored the LCP group at both 3 and 6 months, reflecting better functional recovery and reduced pain. **Conclusion:** LCP offers superior outcomes in terms of union time, complication rates, and functional recovery compared to DCP in displaced midshaft clavicle fractures.

Introduction

The clavicle, a long, S-shaped bone located at the anterior portion of the pectoral girdle, serves as the sole osseous connection between the upper limb and the axial skeleton [1]. It lies directly above the first rib and stretches horizontally across the superior thorax. Structurally, it is characterized by a double curvature—convex medially and concave laterally [2]. The medial end is cone-shaped and articulates with the clavicular notch of the manubrium and the first costal cartilage, forming the sternoclavicular joint [3,28], while the lateral end articulates with the acromion of the scapula

at the acromioclavicular joint [4,29]. These joints are supported by ligaments and muscles, but the middle third of the clavicle, lacking such reinforcement, is particularly prone to fractures. Several muscles attach to the clavicle, contributing to its function and biomechanical complexity. These include the pectoralis major, deltoid, sternocleidomastoid, trapezius, sternohyoid, and subclavius [5–10]. Moreover, the medial third of the clavicle arches over vital neurovascular structures such as the subclavian vessels and the brachial plexus, underscoring the clinical significance of fractures in this region [6]. The clavicle

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receives its blood supply primarily from the suprascapular artery (supplying the lateral portion) and the internal thoracic artery (serving the medial portion) [7]. Functionally, it plays a critical role in shoulder mechanics, maintaining the scapulohumeral rhythm and facilitating upper limb movement. Additionally, it offers protection to underlying neurovascular structures and contributes to the cosmetic contour of the shoulder [8]. Clavicular fractures account for approximately 2.6% of all fractures [30] and 5% of adult fractures, with midshaft fractures comprising 75–80% of these injuries [9]. These fractures are common in young, active males and often result from direct trauma to the shoulder or falls onto an outstretched hand [10]. The typical displacement pattern includes posterolateral migration of the medial fragment due to sternocleidomastoid tension and anteromedial displacement of the lateral fragment due to the weight of the arm and muscular pull [11]. Classification systems such as Neer's and Allman's, as well as the AO system, help in categorizing fractures and guiding treatment. Displaced fractures, especially those with over 2 cm shortening or 100% displacement, are generally considered for surgical management [12]. Treatment of midshaft clavicle fractures has evolved significantly. While nonoperative approaches remain suitable for minimally displaced fractures, operative intervention is increasingly favored due to concerns over nonunion, malunion, and impaired shoulder function [13]. Imaging via X-rays (including Zanca views), chest radiographs, and CT scans is essential for evaluating displacement, comminution, and associated injuries [14]. The primary goal of treatment is to restore

the clavicle's anatomical alignment and function while minimizing complications such as symptomatic nonunion or malunion [15]. Surgical fixation, particularly plate fixation, offers reliable union rates (94–100%) and facilitates early mobilization [16]. Among plating techniques, the superiority of anatomical locking compression plates (LCP) versus dynamic compression plates (DCP) remains a subject of debate [31]. Superior and anteroinferior plating positions are both used, with the latter introduced to reduce symptomatic hardware prominence [17]. This study aims to compare the short-term outcomes of anatomical locking compression plates and dynamic compression plates in the management of displaced midshaft clavicle fractures in adults, focusing on union time, functional recovery using the Quick DASH score, and postoperative complications.

Method

A prospective randomized clinical trial was conducted at Al-Imamein Al-Kadhima'in Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq, over a 12-month period from January 2021 to January 2022. The study enrolled 20 adult patients, aged between 18 and 50 years, presenting with unilateral, closed, displaced midshaft clavicle fractures (>100% displacement and >2 cm shortening), some with skin tenting. Patients were selected from the outpatient clinic and emergency department, then randomly assigned into two equal groups: Group A (n=10) treated with an anatomical locking compression plate (LCP), and Group B (n=10) treated with a dynamic compression plate (DCP).

Figure 1: Preoperative Radiograph AP View Midshaft Clavicle Fracture, Displace with Overlapping with Tenting the Skin. A: Assigned to Group A. B: Assigned to Group B.

Figure 2: Surgical Technique. A: Determination of Landmarks. B: Skin Incision. C & D: Subcutaneous Tissue Release

Figure 3: Isolation and Preservation of Supraclavicular Nerve

Figure 4: Surgical Technique. A: Intra Operative LCP 3.5 mm (Contoured Titanium) with Intact Supraclavicular Nerve. B: Fracture Fixation with 3.5 mm DCP Plate (Stainless Steel). Wash the Surgical Field with Normal Saline Irrigation and Ensure Good Hemostasis. Suturing the Soft Tissue, Subcutaneous Tissue, Skin Suturing without Applying a Drain. The Patient’s Arm was Held in a Sling

Exclusion criteria included open fractures, long-term corticosteroid use, pre-existing functional limitations, polytrauma, neurovascular injuries, floating shoulder, comminuted fractures, and significant medical comorbidities. Preoperatively, all patients underwent detailed clinical and radiological evaluations including AP clavicle X-rays and chest imaging. Blood investigations, virology screening, ECG, and anesthesia assessment were conducted. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Surgery was performed under general anesthesia with patients in the beach chair position. A standard incision was made over the clavicle; the supraclavicular nerve was identified and preserved. In Group A, a 3.5 mm contoured LCP was applied using locking screws; in Group B, a contoured 3.5 mm DCP was used with cortical screws. Fixation aimed for stable anatomical reduction and bicortical purchase with at least three

screws on each side. Postoperatively, patients followed a standardized rehabilitation protocol and were assessed at 2, 6 weeks, 3, and 6 months. Evaluations included radiographic union, Quick-DASH functional score, and complications such as symptomatic hardware or infection. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v27. T-tests and Chi-square tests were used to compare continuous and categorical variables, respectively, with significance set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

A total of 20 patients were enrolled in the current study, the mean age and standard deviation were 26.8 (± 3.9) years. there was no significant difference between the age groups regarding the mean age and mean BMI. Regarding gender, males constituted larger percentage of the sample (65% male, 35% female) as shown in table 1 and table 2.

Table 1: Distribution of the Age and BMI According to the Study Group (Demographic Data)

Characteristics	Group A Group B		P-Value
	Mean (\pm SD*)	Mean (\pm SD*)	
Age (years)	27.5 (± 3.2)	26.1 (± 4.6)	0.442
Body mass index (Kg/m ²)	25.0 (± 1.4)	24.1 (± 1.3)	0.177

Table 2: Distribution of the Gender According to the Study Groups

			Group		Total	P-value
			A	B		
Gender	Male	N	7	6	13	0.542
		%	63.6%	66.7%		
	Female	N	4	3	7	
		%	36.4%	33.3%	35.0%	

Most of the fractures were on the right side, with no significant difference between the study groups. Fractures due to RTA constituted the largest

percentage of the sample (65%), with no significant difference between the study groups regarding the Mechanism of injury, as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of the Side and Mechanism of Injury According to the Study Group

			Group		Total	P-value
			A	B		
Side	Right	N	7	6	13	0.237
		%	63.6%	66.7%	65.0%	
	Left	N	4	3	7	
		%	37.4%	33.3%	35.0%	
Mechanism of injury	RTA	N	6	7	13	0.871
		%	54.5%	77.7%	65.0%	
	Fall down	N	3	1	4	
		%	27.2%	11.1%	20.0%	
	Sport injury	N	2	1	3	
		%	18.2%	11.1%	15.0%	

Regarding the classification of the fracture, type 15.2 A constituted 50% of the sample, type 15.2 B constituted 50%. There was no significant difference between the

study groups regarding the type of fracture, as shown in figure 1 and table 4

Table 4: Distribution of the Fracture Type According to the Study Groups

+			Group		Total	P-value
			A	B		
Classifications	15.2 A	N	6	4	10	0.895
		%	54.5%	44.4%	50.0%	
	15.2 B	N	5	5	10	
		%	45.5%	55.5%	50.0%	
Total	N	11	9	20		
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

Figure 1: Distribution of the Patients According to the Classification of the Fracture

There was no significant difference between the interval from injury to operation in days (P-value > 0.05). as shown in table 5.

Table 5: Interval from Injury to Operation between the Study Groups

characteristics	Group A Group B		P-Value
	Mean (±SD*)	Mean (±SD*)	
Interval from injury to operation (days)	3.0 (1.8)	3.3 (1.7)	0.387

All of clavicle fracture plate fixation patients report Symptomatic hardware (prominence) of the plate, though three patients from group B reports disturbing symptomatic hardware complains compared to only one patient in group A. this is considered as a

significantly lower reporting of Symptomatic hardware (prominence) in Group A compared to Group B (10.1%, 33.3% respectively), (P value < 0.05) as shown in table 6.

Table 6: Symptomatic Hardware (Prominence)

			Group		Total	P-value
			A	B		
Symptomatic hardware (Prominence)	No	N	10	6	16	0.039
		%	90.9 %	66.6%		
	Yes	N	1	3	4	
		%	10.1 %	33.3%		

There was no significant difference in Surgical Site infection as a complication of the surgery between

study groups (9.1%, 11.1% respectively), as shown in table 7.

Table 7: Complication of the Surgery (Surgical Site infection)

			Group		Total	P-value
			A	B		
Surgical Site infection	No	N	9	7	16	0.839
		%	81.9 %	77.8%		
	Yes	N	2	2	4	
		%	18.1 %	22.2%		

Union rate was equal in both groups (100%), all patients in both groups achieved complete union, but the time to union was significantly shorter in the Group A compared to group B (12.3, 15.7 weeks respectively) (P-

value <0.05). The quick DASH was significantly higher in the group B compared to group A at 3 and 6 months postoperatively, as shown in table 8.

Table 8: Time to Union and Quick DASH Score between the Study Groups

Characteristics	Group A Group B		P-Value
	Mean (±SD*)	Mean (±SD*)	
Time to union (weeks)	12.3 (3.4)	15.7 (2.4)	0.020
Quick DASH at 3 months	66.1 (5.2)	78.2 (6.9)	0.003
Quick DASH at 6 months	23.7 (3.4)	36.2 (4.6)	0.001

Discussion

In recent years, there has been a growing shift toward surgical management of displaced midshaft clavicle fractures, aiming to reduce the risk of nonunion and malunion and to improve overall shoulder function [18]. Among the various surgical options, plate fixation has become the most widely adopted approach due to its predictable and favorable outcomes. However, the optimal plating technique—whether anatomical locking compression plate (LCP) or dynamic compression plate (DCP)—remains a matter of ongoing

debate among orthopedic surgeons [19]. This study compared the outcomes of LCP and DCP in the management of displaced midshaft clavicular fractures. The mean age of patients in our sample was 26.8 ± 3.9 years, consistent with findings from a Chinese study indicating that most midshaft clavicle fractures occur in men under the age of 25 [19]. A predominance of male patients (65%) was observed in our study, which aligns with previous research from Korea [20] and China [21]. This trend likely reflects higher exposure of young males to high-energy trauma, including road traffic

accidents (RTA) and sports-related injuries, compared to females who may engage in fewer physical activities due to cultural or lifestyle factors. Regarding fracture healing, the mean time to union in the LCP group (Group A) was 12.3 ± 3.4 weeks, significantly shorter than 15.7 ± 2.4 weeks in the DCP group (Group B). These results are in line with findings from Chul-Hyun Cho in Korea, who reported a mean union time of 13.2 weeks for LCP-treated patients versus 14.6 weeks in other surgical methods [20]. Jiang and Qu also found a union time of 13 weeks with LCP, emphasizing its effectiveness in achieving stable fixation [22]. Similarly, Patil et al. highlighted the advantages of LCP over DCP in terms of faster union and better screw placement in complex fracture patterns [23], and Kameshwar noted that most patients achieved union within 14–20 weeks with LCP [24]. The Quick-DASH scores, used to evaluate functional recovery, were significantly better in the LCP group at both 3 and 6 months postoperatively. This reflects superior physical and psychosocial recovery, a finding supported by similar studies from China and India [20,25], where LCP fixation led to significant postoperative improvement in shoulder function and pain reduction. In terms of complications, symptomatic hardware prominence was more common in the DCP group. This observation supports the findings of Hsiao, who reported lower implant-related complication rates with LCP [26]. However, Patil et al. did not find a significant difference in surgical complications between the two plate types [23], and Kameshwar noted an 8.5% complication rate with LCP alone [24]. Wound site infection rates were comparable in both groups in our study, consistent with the findings by Lai YC and Tarng, who reported similar rates of infection and hardware-related issues between LCP and DCP groups [27]. Overall, this study supports the use of LCP over DCP for better outcomes in terms of union time, functional recovery, and fewer complications, although both methods showed satisfactory union rates.

Conclusion

Group A (LCP) showed significantly shorter union time compared to Group B (DCP), with both achieving 100% union. Quick DASH scores were significantly better in the LCP group at both 3 and 6 months, indicating improved function and less pain. Symptomatic hardware prominence was notably higher in the DCP group. No significant difference was found in postoperative wound infection rates between the two groups.

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